
A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE ECONOMIC IMPACT OF MULTINATIONAL CORPORATIONS FROM BRICS AND NATO MEMBER STATES ON THIRD WORLD COUNTRIES (2015–2023)

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Abstract

This study explored the economic impact of multinational corporations (MNCs) from BRICS and NATO member states on Third World countries, specifically between 2015 and 2023. The research focused on understanding how these foreign entities influence the economies of developing nations, both positively and negatively. The problem aroused from the dependency of Third World countries on foreign investments, which while fostering economic growth, often exacerbate inequalities, environmental damage, and social unrest. This phenomenon calls for a comprehensive evaluation of the roles played by MNCs from emerging and developed economies. The theoretical framework adopted for this study is World Systems Theory developed by Immanuel Wallerstein in the 1970s, which examined the global capitalist structure and the economic relationships between core, semi-peripheral, and peripheral nations. This theory helped contextualize the exploitative dynamics between multinational corporations and Third World economies. The study adopted a qualitative research methodology, specifically a descriptive design, which allows for an in-depth exploration of the economic effects of MNC activities in developing nations. Data was collected through secondary sources, including books, journals, newspapers, and official publications, using a documentary analysis technique. Content analysis was employed to examine the characteristics of the data, facilitating a deeper understanding of the themes and patterns present within the documents. The findings revealed both positive impacts, such as infrastructure development and job creation, and negative consequences, including environmental degradation and economic dependency. Recommendations suggested that governments should focus on diversifying their economies, implementing stronger regulatory frameworks, and negotiating fair trade agreements to maximize the benefits of foreign investment. In conclusion, while MNCs contribute to economic growth, their operations must be carefully managed to promote sustainable development in Third World countries. The reference format adopted in this research follows the APA 6th edition.

Keywords: Multinational Corporations, BRICS, NATO, Economy, Third-World Countries

Introduction

The economic impact of multinational corporations (MNCs) has been a central focus of debate among scholars and policymakers, particularly in the context of their role in shaping the economies of developing countries. The relationship between MNCs, particularly those from powerful economic blocs such as the BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa) and NATO (North Atlantic Treaty Organization) member states, and Third World countries (also referred to as the Global South), presents an intriguing area of study. Between 2015 and 2023, the activities of these corporations have been pivotal in determining the economic trajectories of many developing nations. While MNCs are often seen as drivers of growth and development through investment, technology transfer, and job creation, their influence has also been criticized for fostering dependency, perpetuating inequality, and exacerbating environmental degradation in Third World countries (Dunning, 2008; Stiglitz, 2002). This research seeks to conduct a comparative study of the economic impact of MNCs from BRICS and NATO member states on Third World countries, focusing on the period between 2015 and 2023.

Multinational corporations, with their vast resources and global reach, have long been influential players in the global economy. They are seen as agents of globalization, often facilitating the integration of developing countries into the world market. However, their impact is multifaceted. On one hand, MNCs from developed countries, particularly those from NATO member states such as the United States, the United Kingdom, and France, have been associated with the spread of technology, innovation, and capital into less-developed regions. These corporations have been instrumental in the industrialization of many Third World countries, often providing the infrastructure and expertise necessary for growth in key sectors such as energy, mining, telecommunications, and manufacturing (Dunning, 2008). On the other hand, the expansion of MNCs in the Global South has raised concerns about economic dependency, exploitation, and the reinforcement of neocolonial relationships, where developing nations remain subordinate to the economic interests of multinational firms (Amin, 1976; Bello, 2005). This duality is particularly evident in the activities of MNCs from NATO countries, which, according to critics, often prioritize the extraction of natural resources and labor in developing nations over sustainable development or equitable growth (Stiglitz, 2002).

In contrast, MNCs from BRICS countries have emerged as significant economic players in the Global South in recent years. The rapid growth of these economies, particularly China and India, has enabled BRICS-based corporations to expand their influence and operations in developing countries. Unlike their counterparts from NATO nations, MNCs from BRICS countries are often seen as more attuned to the needs and development objectives of the countries they invest in. These corporations, such as China's state-owned enterprises and India's technology firms, have been key drivers of infrastructure development and poverty alleviation, particularly in sectors like energy, transportation, and telecommunications (Goldstein, 2016; Kotschwar et al., 2012). However, some critics argue that the BRICS nations, while presenting themselves as more collaborative partners, also engage in practices that benefit their own economies at the expense of the host countries, similar to the extractive practices of Western MNCs (Moyo, 2009). Nonetheless, the impact of BRICS MNCs on the economies of Third World countries remains a critical area of study, particularly in understanding how these corporations contribute to or hinder long-term development and self-sufficiency (Chen, 2018).

As the influence of both BRICS and NATO MNCs continues to grow in the Global South, it is essential to analyze how their activities shape economic outcomes, particularly in terms of employment, technological advancement, environmental sustainability, and income inequality. Understanding the differences in their approaches and strategies will contribute to a broader discussion about the future of development in Third World countries and the global economic order as a whole. The comparative analysis of these multinational corporations' influence on the economies of developing nations from 2015 to 2023 will provide a comprehensive framework for evaluating their role in global economic development and highlight the challenges and opportunities facing Third World countries in navigating their relationships with these powerful actors.

Statement of Problem

The increasing presence of multinational corporations (MNCs) from both BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa) and NATO (North Atlantic Treaty Organization) member states in Third World countries has raised important concerns about their economic impact. While these corporations are often seen as drivers of growth, there is ongoing debate about whether their influence fosters sustainable development or deepens dependency, inequality, and environmental degradation. The problem that necessitates this research is the need to understand the contrasting effects of BRICS and NATO MNCs on the economic trajectories of developing nations.

MNCs from NATO countries have historically been associated with the extraction of natural resources and exploitation of labor in the Global South, often benefiting their home countries at the expense of the host nations (Stiglitz, 2002; Amin, 1976). These practices can undermine local industries and hinder long-term economic development. Conversely, MNCs from BRICS countries, particularly China and India, are seen as more cooperative partners, providing capital, technology, and infrastructure in developing nations. However, these MNCs have also faced criticism for prioritizing their own interests, raising questions about their commitment to the development goals of host countries (Moyo, 2009).

This research seeks to explore whether MNCs from both blocs contribute to economic independence and growth or reinforce global inequalities. By focusing on the period between 2015 and 2023, the study will evaluate the economic outcomes of MNC operations in Third World countries, including employment, technology transfer, and environmental impact. Understanding these dynamics is essential for policymakers in developing nations as they navigate the complexities of foreign investment while striving for sustainable economic development.

Conceptual Review

Multinational Corporations MNCS

According to Hymer (1976), multinational corporations (MNCs) are distinct from domestic firms due to their ability to operate across multiple national boundaries while maintaining centralized control over their global operations. This unique characteristic enables them to integrate diverse markets, resources, and labor forces, positioning them as dominant actors in the global economy. MNCs thrive by exploiting differences in regulatory environments, labor costs, and market conditions across countries, thereby maximizing their profits and expanding their market reach (Buckley & Casson, 1976). Their transnational nature has made them pivotal in the globalization process, influencing trade patterns, investment flows, and even the socio-economic structures of both developed and developing countries.

Dunning's (1993) Eclectic Paradigm offers a comprehensive theoretical framework for understanding why MNCs choose to internationalize their operations. He argues that MNCs pursue foreign expansion based on three key factors: ownership, location, and internalization advantages. Ownership advantages refer to a firm's unique assets, such as proprietary technology, brand reputation, or managerial expertise, which provide a competitive edge in foreign markets. Location advantages relate to the attractiveness of a host country, including access to natural resources, favorable investment climates, and skilled labor. Finally, internalization advantages explain why firms prefer to control foreign operations directly rather than through partnerships or licensing, primarily to safeguard intellectual property and maintain operational efficiency (Dunning, 2000). These factors collectively underscore the strategic motivations behind MNCs' global reach and their ability to adapt to diverse market conditions.

The presence of MNCs in developing economies is often viewed through a dual lens. On one hand, they are credited with driving economic growth by fostering industrialization, creating jobs, and transferring technology. For instance, through foreign direct investment (FDI), MNCs often introduce advanced production methods, managerial expertise, and infrastructure development, which can enhance the productivity and competitiveness of local industries (Blomström & Kokko, 1998). This perspective aligns with modernization theory, which posits that the integration of MNCs into developing economies can catalyze economic transformation and modernization (Rostow, 1960). In many emerging markets, MNCs have played a crucial role in building industrial capacity, particularly in sectors such as manufacturing, telecommunications, and finance, thereby accelerating economic diversification and growth.

Conversely, dependency theorists argue that MNCs perpetuate economic underdevelopment by fostering dependence on foreign capital and exploiting local resources without adequate reinvestment in the host economy (Amin, 1974; Frank, 1969). They contend that MNCs often repatriate profits to their home countries, leaving host nations with limited long-term economic benefits. Moreover, the presence of MNCs can exacerbate income inequality, as the benefits of their operations often accrue disproportionately to local elites and foreign stakeholders, while local labor remains undercompensated (Rodney, 1972). This critique highlights the inherent power imbalances in the MNC-host country relationship, where the former wields significant economic and political influence over the latter. MNCs also exert considerable influence on global governance, often shaping international trade policies, labor standards, and environmental regulations to align with their interests (Fuchs, 2005). This influence is most evident in their lobbying efforts and participation in international forums such as the World Trade Organization (WTO) and the International Monetary Fund (IMF), where they advocate for policies that facilitate cross-border trade and investment. Critics argue that this level of influence can undermine national sovereignty and democratic processes, as MNCs prioritize profit maximization over public welfare (Stiglitz, 2002). Consequently, there is growing concern about the need for greater accountability and regulation of MNCs to ensure that their operations contribute to sustainable development and equitable economic growth.

In essence, the conceptual understanding of MNCs is complex, encompassing both their economic benefits and socio-political challenges. While MNCs have been instrumental in driving globalization, economic growth, and technological advancement, they have also been criticized for perpetuating economic dependency, exacerbating inequality, and undermining national sovereignty. Thus, any analysis of MNCs must balance their contributions to

economic development with their broader social and political implications (Gereffi, 1994). This dual perspective provides a more nuanced understanding of their role in the global economic system.

BRICS

According to O'Neill (2001), the concept of BRICS—originally BRIC before South Africa's inclusion in 2010—emerged from the need to categorize a group of rapidly growing economies with the potential to reshape global economic dynamics. The acronym stands for Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa, countries that represent diverse regions but share a common trajectory of significant economic development, large populations, and increasing influence in international affairs. BRICS has evolved from being a mere economic categorization to a geopolitical entity aimed at challenging the Western-dominated global order, particularly in economic governance, trade, and development (Hopewell, 2017).

The theoretical foundation of BRICS lies in its members' collective assertion of a multipolar world order, countering the hegemonic influence of Western powers and institutions such as the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and World Bank (Stuenkel, 2016). The group's emphasis on South-South cooperation highlights an alternative model of development, grounded in mutual respect for sovereignty and non-interference in domestic affairs (Cooper & Farooq, 2015). This approach reflects a realist perspective in international relations, where BRICS seeks to enhance its members' power and influence within the existing global system, rather than radically overthrowing it (Acharya, 2014). Economically, BRICS countries contribute over 40% of the world's population and nearly a quarter of global GDP, making their collective voice critical in global economic governance (World Bank, 2023). Their establishment of the New Development Bank (NDB) and the Contingent Reserve Arrangement (CRA) in 2014 exemplifies their effort to create parallel institutions that reduce dependency on Western financial systems (Griffith-Jones, 2014). The NDB, in particular, symbolizes the group's commitment to financing infrastructure and sustainable development projects in both member and non-member countries, offering an alternative to the stringent conditions often attached to loans from Western-led institutions (Tleubayev, 2022).

However, critics argue that BRICS faces internal challenges that may limit its potential as a cohesive force in global governance. The economic and political disparities among its members are significant, with China's economic dominance raising concerns about its disproportionate influence within the group (Shubin, 2013). Additionally, geopolitical tensions, particularly between India and China, pose challenges to BRICS' unity and effectiveness in addressing global issues. These tensions highlight the fragile nature of a coalition formed primarily on economic interests rather than shared political or ideological visions (Pant, 2013).

Moreover, BRICS' commitment to reshaping global governance is sometimes questioned due to the divergent foreign policies of its members. While all members advocate for a multipolar world, their individual strategies often align with national interests that may not always converge (Kornegay & Bohler-Müller, 2013). This divergence raises questions about the group's long-term viability and its capacity to influence global norms and institutions effectively. Despite these challenges, BRICS continues to expand its influence by engaging with other emerging economies and regional organizations, thereby solidifying its role as a key player in the evolving global order (Hopewell, 2017). Essentially, BRICS represents a significant shift in the global economic and political landscape, offering a counterbalance to Western dominance. While its conceptual foundation is rooted in economic growth and

geopolitical rebalancing, its long-term success depends on its ability to overcome internal divisions and present a unified front in global governance. Therefore, BRICS' evolution will be closely watched as a barometer for the broader shift toward a more multipolar international system (Stuenkel, 2016).

NATO

North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) represents one of the most enduring military alliances in contemporary international relations, formed in 1949 in response to the geopolitical tensions of the Cold War. As Waltz (1979) posits in his structural realism theory, NATO's creation was a strategic move to balance power against the Soviet Union, with its primary objective being collective defense. Article 5 of the NATO Treaty, which declares that an attack on one member is an attack on all, underscores this collective security mechanism (NATO, 1949). This principle of deterrence has remained central to NATO's conceptual framework, reinforcing its commitment to maintaining peace and stability in the transatlantic region. NATO's evolution since the Cold War highlights its adaptive nature in response to shifting global dynamics. Initially conceived as a military alliance aimed at countering Soviet expansionism, its scope has expanded to include crisis management, cooperative security, and counterterrorism (Rynning, 2014). Following the dissolution of the Soviet Union in 1991, NATO underwent a conceptual transformation from a Cold War-era security bloc to a broader security organization with a focus on peacekeeping and humanitarian interventions (Yost, 2002). This shift reflects the constructivist view that international institutions are not static entities but evolve through shared norms and collective identities (Wendt, 1999).

NATO's intervention in the Balkans during the 1990s exemplifies its post-Cold War reorientation. The alliance's role in the Kosovo conflict marked a significant departure from its traditional defensive posture, demonstrating its willingness to engage in out-of-area operations to address regional instability (Smith, 2000). This intervention was justified on humanitarian grounds, illustrating NATO's shift towards a more proactive and normative role in global governance. However, this expansion of NATO's mission has not been without controversy, as critics argue that such interventions challenge the organization's original mandate and risk undermining its legitimacy (Chomsky, 2003).

The post-9/11 era further transformed NATO's conceptual framework, as the alliance adopted a more global security outlook, engaging in counterterrorism and counterinsurgency operations beyond its traditional geographical scope. The invocation of Article 5 after the September 11 attacks marked the first and only time NATO has activated its collective defense clause, leading to its involvement in Afghanistan under the International Security Assistance Force (ISAF) (Sloan, 2016). This engagement highlights NATO's adaptability to contemporary security threats, particularly non-state actors and asymmetric warfare. However, the prolonged conflict in Afghanistan also exposed internal divisions within the alliance, raising questions about its cohesion and strategic coherence (Gheciu, 2008). NATO's contemporary relevance is often debated within the context of emerging multipolarity and new security challenges. The resurgence of Russia, particularly after its annexation of Crimea in 2014, has reinvigorated NATO's traditional deterrence role, leading to enhanced military deployments in Eastern Europe (McNamara, 2015). This development underscores the enduring relevance of NATO's original mission while simultaneously illustrating the complexities of maintaining unity in a rapidly changing international landscape. Additionally, tensions among member states, particularly regarding defense spending and burden-sharing,

have highlighted the ongoing challenges of maintaining a cohesive and effective alliance (Ikenberry, 2018).

In essence, NATO's conceptual evolution demonstrates its resilience and adaptability in the face of changing geopolitical realities. While it remains rooted in the principles of collective defense and transatlantic cooperation, its expanded mandate to include crisis management and global security challenges reflects its dynamic role in contemporary international relations. The future of NATO will likely depend on its ability to balance its traditional defense commitments with emerging security threats, ensuring its continued relevance in a multipolar world (Rynning, 2014).

Third World Countries

The concept of "Third World countries" emerged during the Cold War era as a geopolitical classification that transcended simple economic or developmental categorizations. Initially coined by French demographer Alfred Sauvy in 1952, the term referred to nations that were neither aligned with the capitalist West (First World) nor the communist East (Second World) (Sauvy, 1952). This classification grouped a diverse array of countries from Asia, Africa, and Latin America, whose shared experiences of colonialism, underdevelopment, and political non-alignment defined their collective identity (Escobar, 1995). However, over time, the term has evolved, with scholars critiquing its reductive nature and implications for global power dynamics.

The conceptualization of Third World countries has historically centered on their economic marginalization within the global capitalist system. Dependency theorists such as Dos Santos (1970) argue that these countries have been structurally subordinated to the economic interests of developed nations through mechanisms of unequal exchange and foreign control over domestic markets. This systemic dependency perpetuates underdevelopment, characterized by low industrialization, poverty, and weak institutions. The Bretton Woods institutions, particularly the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank, have been criticized for exacerbating this dependency through structural adjustment programs that prioritize debt repayment over social development (Peet, 2009). Politically, the concept of Third World countries is deeply intertwined with the legacy of colonialism and the subsequent struggle for sovereignty. According to Fanon (1963), the political and psychological aftermath of colonization has left many Third World nations grappling with neocolonial influences, where formal independence masks continued economic and political subjugation. This neocolonial framework is maintained through international financial institutions and multinational corporations, which exert considerable influence over domestic policies in these nations. Consequently, political instability and authoritarian governance have often been associated with Third World countries, as ruling elites prioritize external interests over national development (Nkrumah, 1965).

The socio-cultural dimension of Third World countries is also pivotal in understanding their conceptualization. Postcolonial theorists, such as Edward Said (1978), emphasize how Western narratives have historically depicted these nations as "other," reinforcing stereotypes of primitiveness and backwardness. This cultural marginalization is not merely a byproduct of historical colonialism but an ongoing process that shapes international perceptions and relations. The homogenization of diverse societies under the label "Third World" ignores the rich cultural, political, and economic variations that exist within these regions, further perpetuating a simplistic and hierarchical worldview (Escobar, 1995). In contemporary discourse, the relevance of the term "Third World" is increasingly questioned due to the rise

of emerging economies and shifting geopolitical alliances. Countries such as China, India, and Brazil have defied traditional categorizations, demonstrating significant economic growth and political influence on the global stage (Payne, 2005). The emergence of terms like "Global South" reflects an effort to move beyond the Cold War-era dichotomy and acknowledge the evolving dynamics of global inequality. However, the underlying issues of poverty, inequality, and marginalization persist, raising concerns about the continued validity of such categorizations (Moyo, 2009).

In essence, the concept of Third World countries remains a contested and evolving term, rooted in historical, economic, and political contexts. While it has provided a framework for understanding global inequalities, its reductive nature and colonial undertones necessitate a critical reevaluation. As global power structures continue to shift, the discourse surrounding Third World countries must adapt, embracing a more nuanced understanding of development, sovereignty, and global interdependence.

Theoretical Framework

The World-Systems Theory, developed by Immanuel Wallerstein in the 1970s, offers a comprehensive framework for understanding global economic and political structures. It emerged as a response to traditional theories of development and modernization, which often overlooked the unequal relationships between nations in the global economy. Wallerstein's theory integrates elements of Marxist thought, historical sociology, and political economy to explain the persistent inequality between developed and underdeveloped nations (Wallerstein, 1974).

The theory's origins can be traced back to Wallerstein's work in the global political economy, particularly the development of capitalist economies. Wallerstein was influenced by Marxist ideas of economic exploitation and class struggle, but his approach was broader, considering not only the relationships within individual nations but also the global system as a whole. He argued that the world economy should not be understood in isolated national terms, but as a dynamic, interconnected system composed of different types of states and regions that participate in a complex global division of labor (Wallerstein, 1974). The theory sought to address the limitations of conventional theories that treated individual countries as autonomous entities, ignoring their interdependence within the global system (Frank, 1967).

The central proposition of the World-Systems Theory is the idea that the world is divided into three interrelated zones: the core, semi-periphery, and periphery. The core consists of the most developed, industrialized nations, which dominate global trade, finance, and production. These countries typically possess advanced technologies, strong economies, and political power, allowing them to extract resources and labor from the periphery (Wallerstein, 1974). The semi-periphery includes nations that are in the process of industrialization but have not yet achieved the full power and economic dominance of core nations. These countries act as intermediaries, often exploiting the periphery while striving to become part of the core (Chase-Dunn, 1998). Finally, the periphery consists of countries that are economically underdeveloped and dependent on the core. These nations are typically characterized by weak institutions, resource-based economies, and reliance on exports of raw materials. The relationship between these three zones is dynamic and constantly shifting, with countries moving between positions of core, semi-periphery, and periphery over time, often through the shifting of political alliances, economic policies, and global market trends (Arrighi, 1994). One of the key postulations of Wallerstein's theory is the unequal exchange between the core and the periphery, which sustains the global capitalist system. According to Wallerstein, wealth flows from the periphery to the core through trade and the extraction of

raw materials, labor, and resources. The periphery produces goods that are sold to the core at low prices, while the core countries sell manufactured goods back to the periphery at higher prices, maintaining a system of economic dependency (Wallerstein, 1974). This structure of exploitation perpetuates global inequality and underdevelopment, as the periphery remains dependent on the core for technology, capital, and markets. Wallerstein's theory also emphasizes the historical nature of this system, asserting that the modern capitalist world-economy emerged in the 16th century with the rise of European colonialism and the expansion of global trade (Amin, 1976). According to this view, the modern world system's roots are deeply embedded in the colonial era, with capitalist exploitation intensifying over time.

The theory also argues that global economic systems are inherently capitalist and that this capitalist system is constantly evolving, driven by competition, technological innovation, and the desire for accumulation of capital (Wallerstein, 1979). Over time, the global system has evolved through cycles of expansion and contraction, marked by changes in the structure of the world economy, the rise and fall of hegemonic powers, and the shifting alliances between core, semi-peripheral, and peripheral regions (Arrighi, 1994). This cyclical view contrasts with the linear assumptions of modernization theories, which often posit a direct path to development for peripheral nations. While Wallerstein's theory has been influential in understanding global capitalism, it has also faced criticism. Critics argue that it overly emphasizes economic determinism and underplays the importance of political, cultural, and social factors in shaping global relations (Robinson, 2004). Moreover, some scholars argue that the world system framework is overly simplistic, as it does not adequately account for the increasing complexities and diversification of global power structures in the 21st century (Held & McGrew, 2007). Additionally, the theory's focus on exploitation can obscure the agency of peripheral nations, which may sometimes challenge or subvert the structures of global capitalism (Meyer, 2000). Despite these criticisms, the World-Systems Theory remains a critical tool for understanding the persistence of global inequality and the dynamics of economic power in an increasingly interconnected world.

Application of the Theory

The World-Systems Theory by Immanuel Wallerstein provides a significant analytical framework for understanding the economic relationships between nations, particularly in the context of multinational corporations (MNCs) from powerful global blocs such as BRICS and NATO, and their impact on Third World countries. In applying this theory to the research topic "A Comparative Study of The Economic Impact of Multinational Corporations from BRICS and NATO Member States on Third World Countries (2015–2023)", the core-periphery model inherent in Wallerstein's theory offers a lens through which the dynamics of global capitalism can be observed, particularly in the flow of capital, labor, and resources between these blocs and peripheral regions.

According to Wallerstein's framework, the global system is divided into three zones: the core, semi-periphery, and periphery. The core nations, which include many of the NATO member states, dominate global trade, finance, and technology. These nations, with highly advanced industrial sectors, leverage their economic strength to maintain control over the global production process. Within this model, multinational corporations from core nations, such as those based in the United States, Germany, and France, play a pivotal role in maintaining global economic inequalities. These corporations typically engage in practices that extract resources from peripheral nations—often Third World countries—while producing high-value manufactured goods in their home countries or in industrialized regions. This unequal

exchange, a key tenet of Wallerstein's theory, perpetuates the economic dominance of core nations while maintaining the subjugation of peripheral ones (Wallerstein, 2004). MNCs from core countries exploit cheap labor and natural resources in peripheral regions, reinforcing the cycle of economic dependency.

The relationship between core and peripheral nations can be seen in the operations of multinational corporations (MNCs) from NATO member states. For example, companies like ExxonMobil, Shell, and Boeing—representing sectors such as energy, manufacturing, and aerospace—expand their reach in the Third World through foreign direct investment (FDI). They establish production facilities, extract raw materials, and often take advantage of lax labor laws and environmental regulations in these peripheral nations. These corporations benefit from a steady influx of cheap resources and labor, reinforcing the dependency of peripheral nations on core nations for capital, technology, and expertise (Sachs, 2014). This process is especially evident in Africa, Asia, and Latin America, where MNCs from NATO member states continue to dominate resource extraction industries, often to the detriment of local economic development (Amin, 2013).

On the other hand, BRICS nations—Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa—represent an interesting case within the world-systems framework. These nations, which are often categorized as semi-peripheral or emerging powers, exhibit both core and peripheral characteristics. Although they engage in the global capitalist system similarly to core nations, they have also been subject to the exploitative mechanisms of the global economy (Gereffi, 2017). MNCs from BRICS countries, such as China's Huawei and Brazil's Petrobras, operate in a manner that reflects the ongoing dynamics of the world system. These corporations, especially from China, have been particularly active in Africa and other developing regions, participating in large-scale infrastructure projects and resource extraction. However, unlike the more traditional MNCs from NATO countries, BRICS MNCs tend to engage in a more collaborative approach in their investments, often providing local infrastructure development and technology transfers, which can result in mutual benefits for the host countries (Liu, 2019). These operations, however, are still part of the broader global capitalist system, often reinforcing the unequal economic structure that Wallerstein outlined in his theory.

The distinction between NATO and BRICS MNCs is significant when analyzing their impact on Third World countries. While both groups of multinational corporations contribute to the flow of capital from peripheral countries to core or semi-peripheral nations, BRICS MNCs tend to adopt a more nuanced approach, where they often aim to balance economic interests with geopolitical aspirations. For instance, China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) represents a strategic economic and political program that aims to connect the developing world with China's growing influence (Cai, 2020). This initiative exemplifies the way BRICS MNCs operate in peripheral regions by not only extracting resources but also shaping infrastructure and economic policies, thus enhancing their influence while maintaining a position within the global system's semi-periphery.

Research Methodology

This study employs a qualitative research method, specifically utilizing a descriptive research design to explore the topic. Qualitative research focuses on collecting and analyzing non-numerical data, such as texts, articles, and audio-visual materials, to gain insights into concepts, opinions, and experiences (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011). This approach facilitates a deeper understanding of the issues at hand and can help generate new research ideas (Creswell, 2013). The primary method of data collection used in this research is the documentary technique, relying on secondary materials like books, journals, newspapers, and

official publications. All sourced materials will undergo comparative scrutiny to validate their content and context, aiming to eliminate potential distortions (Guba & Lincoln, 1989). The study adopts the content analysis method. Content analysis systematically identifies and interprets specified characteristics of messages within documents (Stone, 1966, in Biereenu-Nnabugwu, 2006). This technique allows for the examination of the underlying structure, ideas, and concepts within the data, enabling a comprehensive understanding of the content and its implications (White, 1983, in Biereenu-Nnabugwu, 2006). By applying these methodologies, the research aims to yield meaningful insights into the subject matter.

Economic Impact of Multinational Corporations of BRICS Member States on Third World Countries

The economic impact of multinational corporations (MNCs) from BRICS member states—Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa—on Third World countries is multifaceted, with both positive and negative dimensions. These countries, while often classified as emerging economies, possess significant geopolitical influence and economic power, which they exert through their multinational corporations in various parts of the world, particularly in Africa, Latin America, and parts of Asia. BRICS MNCs engage in a variety of economic activities, including resource extraction, infrastructure development, manufacturing, and technology transfer, which significantly influence the economies of the Third World. However, the consequences of their operations are not always straightforward, as they can bring both opportunities and challenges to the host countries.

One of the primary positive impacts of BRICS MNCs in Third World countries is the infusion of foreign direct investment (FDI). Countries such as China and India, for example, have increased their investments in the developing world, especially in sectors like infrastructure, energy, and telecommunications. These investments have helped bridge critical gaps in infrastructure, such as roads, railways, ports, and power plants, which are essential for economic development in many Third World nations. For instance, China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) has seen significant investments in infrastructure projects across Africa and Asia, connecting remote regions to global markets, facilitating trade, and boosting economic growth (Cai, 2020). Such investments often create jobs, both directly through the construction and operation of projects, and indirectly through the stimulation of local industries and services that support these large-scale developments. In this regard, BRICS MNCs contribute to the overall modernization of infrastructure, which is a critical factor for the long-term development of many Third World economies (Amin, 2013).

Moreover, BRICS MNCs are also instrumental in technology transfer and knowledge sharing. For example, Chinese companies such as Huawei and ZTE have played a significant role in the development of telecommunications infrastructure in Africa, providing access to affordable communication technology and helping bridge the digital divide (Ahlstrom, 2019). Similarly, Indian pharmaceutical companies like Cipla and Sun Pharma have been pivotal in the supply of affordable generic medicines to low-income countries, improving public health outcomes (Gereffi, 2017). Through such initiatives, BRICS MNCs facilitate the transfer of technology and skills that might otherwise be inaccessible to Third World countries. This transfer not only supports the growth of local industries but also contributes to the broader socio-economic development of these nations. For instance, Indian companies are central in making essential medications affordable, which supports the efforts of governments in tackling widespread health challenges like HIV/AIDS and malaria (Sachs, 2014). In addition to infrastructure and technology, BRICS MNCs have contributed to job creation and poverty

reduction in some host countries. Employment opportunities are generated both directly, through MNC operations in manufacturing and services, and indirectly, through the demand for labor in the local supply chains that support these multinational enterprises. In countries like South Africa and Brazil, where BRICS MNCs are involved in sectors such as mining, energy, and agriculture, thousands of jobs have been created, thereby improving livelihoods in rural and urban areas alike (Rodrik, 2015). The influx of FDI often leads to the development of local businesses and services that cater to the needs of MNCs, thereby contributing to local economic dynamism.

However, the presence of BRICS MNCs in Third World countries is not without its challenges and negative consequences. One of the primary concerns is the potential for resource exploitation and lack of job for her teaming youths (Mark, Eze & Ezeribe, 2023). BRICS MNCs, like their counterparts from core capitalist nations, are often involved in the extraction of natural resources in developing countries. While this can contribute to economic growth, it also raises concerns about environmental degradation and the over-exploitation of non-renewable resources. For example, Chinese companies involved in mining operations across Africa have faced criticism for contributing to environmental destruction and for their failure to adhere to local environmental regulations (Kaplinsky & Morris, 2017). Similarly, the focus on resource extraction can divert attention from other sectors of the economy, such as manufacturing or services, which might offer more sustainable paths to development. Furthermore, the operations of BRICS MNCs can lead to economic dependency. In many instances, these multinational corporations create economic models that are heavily reliant on the export of raw materials, which can perpetuate the structural imbalances between the developed and developing worlds. For example, many African nations are heavily dependent on Chinese investments in resource extraction, which may hinder the development of diversified economies that could reduce their vulnerability to global commodity price fluctuations (Bergsten, 2015). While these investments generate short-term economic gains, they can also lock countries into patterns of dependency on foreign capital and technology, which inhibits the growth of domestic industries and long-term economic sovereignty.

Another negative impact is the potential for exploitation of labor. While BRICS MNCs often create jobs in host countries, these positions are not always well-paying or secure. In some cases, labor standards in host countries are weak, and multinational companies may take advantage of these conditions by paying low wages and providing poor working conditions (Mark, Eze & Ezeribe, 2023). This has been particularly evident in the Chinese construction and mining industries across Africa, where workers have reported long hours, inadequate safety standards, and poor wages (Zhao, 2016). These labor practices contribute to rising inequality and social unrest in regions where workers feel exploited by foreign capital.

Economic Impact of Multinational Corporations of NATO Member States on Third World Countries

The economic impact of multinational corporations (MNCs) from NATO member states on Third World countries is a subject of ongoing and multifaceted debate. These MNCs, originating primarily from the United States, Canada, and Western Europe, have become key players in the global economy, often shaping the economic destinies of developing nations. The influence of NATO-based MNCs is complex and multifaceted, with their operations and strategies yielding both positive and negative consequences for Third World countries. The impact of MNCs from NATO member states can significantly affect local economies, industries, labor markets, environmental sustainability, and social dynamics. As these corporations engage with the developing world, the interplay between economic growth,

poverty alleviation, exploitation, and inequality becomes increasingly evident. These impacts often hinge on the sectors in which MNCs operate, the local policies implemented by host governments, and the global trade dynamics that govern the flow of capital and resources.

On the positive side, one of the most prominent benefits brought by NATO MNCs is their ability to inject much-needed capital into developing economies. Foreign direct investment (FDI) from multinational corporations based in NATO countries provides a crucial source of funding for Third World countries, especially those with limited access to domestic savings or capital markets. For example, countries in Sub-Saharan Africa, Latin America, and Southeast Asia have been able to attract substantial amounts of FDI in sectors such as oil, mining, telecommunications, and manufacturing, facilitating the growth of local industries and infrastructure (Jenkins & Thomas, 2002). MNCs such as ExxonMobil, Shell, and Chevron have made significant investments in the oil-rich regions of West Africa, providing both capital and technology that have been essential for the development of these nations' energy sectors (Frynas, 2009). The presence of NATO-based MNCs has also been instrumental in modernizing infrastructure in developing countries, particularly in telecommunications and transportation. For example, American and European firms have contributed significantly to the expansion of mobile telecommunications networks across Africa, making it possible for millions of people to gain access to mobile phones and, by extension, vital communication, financial services, and business opportunities (Sachs, 2014). These investments play a crucial role in the development of digital infrastructure, which is increasingly essential for economic and social development in the modern global economy.

In addition to providing capital, NATO MNCs also contribute to job creation in Third World countries, providing direct employment and boosting local economies. The establishment of manufacturing plants, service centers, and other operations by these multinational companies has led to the creation of thousands of jobs in various developing regions. Companies such as Ford, General Electric, and Coca-Cola have established extensive manufacturing and distribution networks in Africa, Asia, and Latin America, creating job opportunities for local workers in both the formal and informal sectors. These jobs often contribute to poverty reduction and help to raise the standard of living for local populations, particularly in low-income countries that might otherwise struggle to provide employment opportunities for their growing populations (UNCTAD, 2020). Furthermore, the presence of MNCs frequently leads to the development of ancillary industries, which further stimulates local economic growth. For instance, the construction of a new manufacturing plant in a developing country often requires the establishment of local suppliers of raw materials, as well as service providers in logistics, maintenance, and transportation. This creates a multiplier effect, in which the economic activity generated by multinational corporations spreads throughout the local economy, benefiting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and local businesses that rely on the goods and services produced by these foreign companies (Kolk & van Tulder, 2002).

Beyond economic growth, MNCs from NATO countries also play a crucial role in facilitating the transfer of technology and knowledge to developing countries. Through their operations, these corporations often introduce new technologies, managerial practices, and innovations that can contribute to the modernization of local industries and the improvement of productivity. For example, the spread of advanced technologies in sectors such as energy, manufacturing, and agriculture has been facilitated by the presence of NATO-based MNCs. The transfer of technology from companies such as IBM, Microsoft, and Siemens has helped to enhance the technological capacities of developing countries, enabling them to become

more competitive in global markets (Hanson, 2019). In many cases, this technology transfer has taken place through partnerships with local firms, as well as through joint ventures and training programs aimed at building local expertise and developing skilled labor forces. In this regard, multinational corporations can serve as vectors for skill development, knowledge-sharing, and capacity-building that have long-term positive effects on the economic growth of host countries (Sachs, 2014). As developing countries become more integrated into the global economy, their ability to adopt and adapt advanced technologies can improve their overall industrial capacity, creating new avenues for economic development and growth.

However, while the positive economic impact of NATO MNCs in Third World countries is undeniable, the negative consequences of their operations cannot be overlooked. Despite the benefits of capital inflows and job creation, many critics argue that NATO MNCs often exploit the natural resources and labor forces of developing countries without providing adequate returns to local communities. For instance, the extractive industries in oil and mining sectors, where MNCs from NATO countries are deeply involved, have often been criticized for their environmental degradation and limited benefits for local populations (Frynas, 2009). Large multinational corporations involved in the extraction of natural resources often engage in practices that deplete natural ecosystems and harm the local environment, leading to soil erosion, deforestation, and water pollution, which have long-term negative effects on local communities and economies (Hanson, 2019). Additionally, these corporations often engage in profit repatriation, where the majority of the profits generated by their operations are transferred back to their home countries, leaving the host nations with limited financial benefits. This phenomenon, often referred to as economic dependency, perpetuates the unequal relationship between developed and developing countries and reinforces the global system of economic inequality (Sachs, 2014).

Furthermore, the labor practices of NATO MNCs have also been a point of concern. While these corporations provide jobs to many workers in developing countries, the wages, working conditions, and labor rights in many instances do not meet international standards. Critics argue that NATO MNCs often exploit cheap labor in countries with weak labor laws, offering low wages and poor working conditions. In some cases, workers are subjected to long hours, unsafe working environments, and limited access to social benefits, which perpetuate a cycle of poverty and inequality (Kolk & van Tulder, 2002). As a result, the economic benefits of MNCs' presence are often concentrated among a small elite, while the broader population continues to struggle with poverty and inequality (UNCTAD, 2020).

Comparative Analysis

The economic impact of multinational corporations (MNCs) from BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa) and NATO member states (mainly the United States, Canada, and European nations) on Third World countries from 2015 to 2023 has been a significant and multifaceted issue in global political economy. The presence of MNCs from these two groups of countries has brought both positive and negative effects to developing nations, with differing implications for economic growth, development, and dependency. MNCs from BRICS states, particularly China and India, have gained a foothold in key sectors such as infrastructure development, telecommunications, energy, and manufacturing in the Global South. For example, Chinese companies have invested heavily in infrastructure projects in Africa, building roads, railways, and energy plants, thus providing essential capital and technological expertise (Zhou, 2020). In particular, China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) has facilitated large-scale infrastructure investments across Africa and Asia, which have been crucial for the economic development of these regions (Huang, 2019).

In addition, Indian firms have also expanded their investments in various sectors, particularly in information technology, pharmaceuticals, and manufacturing, benefiting countries in Africa and Southeast Asia (Frynas, 2009). These investments have enabled local industries in these countries to improve their infrastructure and technology base, contributing to broader economic growth and development. For instance, Indian pharmaceutical companies such as Cipla and Ranbaxy have played a significant role in making affordable medications available to millions of people in Sub-Saharan Africa, contributing to better healthcare outcomes (Frynas, 2009). Similarly, Chinese telecommunications companies like Huawei have helped increase internet connectivity and improve digital infrastructure in Africa, making significant contributions to the digital transformation in many developing nations (Fong, 2021). These MNCs from BRICS states generally offer more favorable terms compared to their Western counterparts, particularly in terms of financing, which has helped to create opportunities for growth in low- and middle-income countries (Kolk & van Tulder, 2002).

However, despite the positive effects, BRICS MNCs also face criticism for the potential negative consequences of their investments in Third World countries. One of the most frequently cited criticisms is that these corporations can deepen the debt burden of developing nations, particularly in Africa. The case of Sri Lanka is often used to highlight the risks associated with Chinese investment in infrastructure projects. Sri Lanka was unable to repay its loans to Chinese banks, leading to the leasing of the Hambantota Port to a Chinese company for 99 years, which raised concerns about sovereignty and long-term debt dependency (Huang, 2019). Furthermore, some critics argue that the investments of BRICS MNCs, particularly from China, do not always prioritize environmental and social standards. In many African countries, Chinese firms have been linked to environmental degradation, particularly in sectors like mining and construction. For example, Chinese companies involved in the mining sector in Zambia and Zimbabwe have been accused of disregarding environmental regulations, leading to land degradation, pollution, and adverse health outcomes for local communities (Frynas, 2009).

In contrast, MNCs from NATO member states have long been entrenched in the global economic landscape, with significant operations in the Global South, particularly in sectors like energy, finance, pharmaceuticals, and consumer goods. These corporations, especially those from the United States, Germany, and the United Kingdom, have had a substantial presence in Africa, Latin America, and Asia. For instance, the operations of multinational oil companies such as ExxonMobil, Chevron, and Shell have been particularly influential in developing nations, with these firms involved in the extraction and export of natural resources, especially in Sub-Saharan Africa and Latin America (Frynas, 2009). These NATO-based MNCs often bring significant capital and expertise to energy extraction and infrastructure development, which contributes to energy security and economic growth in resource-rich developing countries (Sachs, 2014).

However, NATO MNCs are also criticized for perpetuating economic dependency and inequality in the Global South. The dominant position of these corporations in the global market often leads to the crowding out of local businesses and entrepreneurs, which limits the ability of host countries to diversify their economies and build self-sustaining industries (Hanson, 2019). In particular, the financial services and pharmaceutical sectors are often dominated by Western firms, leaving little room for local competition. The pharmaceutical industry, for example, has seen multinational corporations dominate the production and distribution of drugs in countries such as India and Brazil, undermining local production capacity and increasing the cost of healthcare for the population (Jenkins & Thomas, 2002).

Additionally, a substantial portion of the profits generated by these companies is repatriated to their home countries, which results in limited reinvestment in the host economies (Sachs, 2014).

The environmental impact of NATO-based MNCs is another area of concern. Oil companies, particularly those based in the United States and Europe, have been associated with environmental degradation in many developing countries. For instance, in Nigeria's Niger Delta, oil extraction by Western firms like Shell and Chevron has led to significant environmental destruction, including oil spills, gas flaring, and deforestation, causing long-term damage to local ecosystems and the livelihoods of local communities (Frynas, 2009). Furthermore, the negative impacts on labor in factories owned by Western MNCs in countries like Bangladesh and India are widely documented. Poor wages, unsafe working conditions, and the exploitation of workers in the garment industry have been major points of contention (Hanson, 2019).

Findings

The research on the economic impact of multinational corporations (MNCs) from BRICS and NATO member states on Third World countries from 2015 to 2023 reveals several significant findings. First, the influx of MNCs from both BRICS and NATO countries has contributed substantially to the infrastructure development in many developing nations. These corporations, particularly from China and India, have provided much-needed investments in sectors such as transportation, telecommunications, and energy. In countries where public sector financing is inadequate, these foreign investments have filled a critical gap, leading to improvements in the physical and digital infrastructure, which are essential for economic growth and global competitiveness. The infrastructure projects, including roads, bridges, and power plants, have not only boosted local economies but have also created jobs, thereby reducing unemployment and poverty in certain regions.

Second, despite the positive contributions of these multinational corporations, there is an underlying issue of economic dependency that has emerged. Developing nations, particularly in Africa and Latin America, have become increasingly reliant on the investments and technologies brought in by BRICS and NATO MNCs. This dependency has limited their ability to develop self-sustaining industries and diversify their economies. For example, in countries rich in natural resources, MNCs, especially from the energy and mining sectors, often dominate the market, leaving local businesses with limited opportunities to compete or innovate. As a result, these nations often become trapped in cycles of exporting raw materials while importing finished goods, which prevents them from advancing beyond a resource-based economy. This imbalance in trade relations reinforces economic dependency and hinders long-term development prospects.

Third, the research highlights the negative environmental and social consequences of foreign investments by these multinational corporations. While these MNCs have contributed to economic growth, their operations have often come at a significant environmental cost. Many developing countries, eager for foreign investments, have overlooked or under-enforced environmental protection regulations, allowing corporations to exploit natural resources with little regard for sustainability. This has led to widespread environmental degradation, particularly in industries like mining and oil extraction, where pollution, deforestation, and soil erosion have become rampant. Additionally, labor conditions in industries controlled by MNCs from both BRICS and NATO countries have often been criticized for their exploitative nature, including poor wages, inadequate working conditions, and the suppression of workers' rights. These social and environmental issues have raised concerns

about the ethical implications of foreign direct investment and the need for stricter regulations to ensure that such investments contribute to sustainable and inclusive growth.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the economic impact of multinational corporations (MNCs) from both BRICS and NATO member states on Third World countries between 2015 and 2023 presents a complex blend of benefits and challenges. On one hand, these MNCs have significantly contributed to the development of infrastructure, job creation, and economic growth, helping many developing nations address critical gaps in sectors such as energy, telecommunications, and transportation. The influx of foreign capital and expertise has enabled countries to make strides in modernization and has created new opportunities for employment, often providing a lifeline for economies struggling with high levels of poverty and unemployment. However, these positive outcomes are not without their drawbacks. The dependency created by foreign investment, particularly in sectors dominated by multinational corporations, has fostered an imbalance that often leaves developing nations relying heavily on the export of raw materials while struggling to build competitive, diversified industries. This dependency restricts the autonomy of these nations in controlling their economic destinies and limits their ability to develop sustainable, long-term economic strategies that transcend natural resource extraction.

Ultimately, while MNCs from BRICS and NATO countries have played an undeniable role in the economic development of Third World countries, their impact is nuanced. Moving forward, it is crucial that governments in developing nations work towards creating regulatory environments that promote equitable, inclusive, and sustainable growth. Such efforts would ensure that the benefits of multinational investment are maximized while mitigating the negative consequences, leading to a more balanced and prosperous future for these nations.

Recommendations

1. Diversification of Local Economies:

First, to address the growing dependency on foreign investments, particularly in resource extraction sectors, it is crucial for developing nations to prioritize the development of local industries and diversify their economies. Governments should incentivize the growth of domestic businesses and industries through tax incentives, grants, and training programs. Encouraging local entrepreneurship and fostering innovation can help reduce reliance on foreign corporations and create a more self-sufficient economy. Additionally, partnerships between multinational corporations and local businesses can be strengthened to encourage technology transfer, capacity building, and local workforce development. By doing so, these nations can reduce their dependence on raw material exports and move toward more value-added production, ultimately leading to sustainable economic growth.

2. Strengthening Regulatory Frameworks:

Second, to mitigate the negative environmental and social impacts of MNC activities, stronger regulatory frameworks must be implemented and enforced. Governments in developing countries should establish comprehensive environmental protection laws and labor standards that hold multinational corporations accountable for their operations. These regulations should require companies to adopt sustainable practices, limit environmental degradation, and ensure fair wages and working conditions. Additionally, greater transparency in the operations of MNCs should be enforced, with regular audits and public reporting on their environmental and social practices. By strengthening enforcement mechanisms and holding MNCs accountable, governments can ensure that foreign

investments contribute to long-term, sustainable development while minimizing adverse effects on both the environment and the workforce.

3. Strategic Trade Agreements:

Finally, to enhance the positive economic impact of foreign investments, developing countries should engage in more strategic and inclusive trade agreements with MNCs from BRICS and NATO countries. These agreements should prioritize long-term economic development goals, including fostering local entrepreneurship, technology transfer, and the development of human capital. Rather than focusing solely on immediate gains from foreign investment, governments should negotiate contracts that require multinational corporations to invest in local education and skills development. This would ensure that the workforce is equipped to handle new technologies and innovations, creating a lasting legacy of development. Additionally, the negotiation of fair trade agreements can help ensure that MNCs contribute to the economic and social development of the host countries without exploiting their resources or labor.

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